

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HARD GELATIN CAPSULES OF ENZALUTAMIDE FOR ENHANCEMENT OF ORAL BIOAVAILABILITY

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Abstract:

Enzalutamide is a BCS class II drug characterized by low solubility, resulting in low bioavailability. In the current study, Enzalutamide was successfully formulated into hard gelatin capsules using a conventional process with two solubilizers, Captex and Labrasol, in an optimized ratio to achieve the desired dissolution. The dissolution increased with a higher ratio of solubilizers, specifically the combination of Labrasol and Captex. These developed compositions demonstrated an improved dissolution rate, thereby enhancing bioavailability. Additionally, the study provided a solution containing a polymer and a surfactant, which includes a mixture of fatty and sterol compounds in a water-miscible solvent. When diluted with an aqueous vehicle, this solution forms a nano dispersion of Enzalutamide. Stability tests showed no significant changes in the formulation after six months, indicating stability. In vitro dissolution studies revealed a notable improvement in the dissolution behavior of these innovative formulations. Overall, the investigation highlighted that these novel formulations offer a promising approach for improving the oral absorption and bioavailability of BCS class II drugs

key words: Enzalutamide, Prostate Cancer, Labrasol, captex, hard gelatin capsule.

INTRODUCTION:

Prostate cancer is one of the most prevalent cancers among men, particularly affecting older individuals. It originates in the prostate gland, which is responsible for producing seminal fluid. Typically, prostate cancer progresses slowly and may remain confined to the gland, posing minimal immediate threat. However, certain aggressive forms can rapidly metastasize, necessitating timely intervention.

Enzalutamide molecule is practically insoluble in water and BCS Class-II drugs. Because of the low solubility, the dissolution rate is poor, and drugs have low bioavailability. The present research work was aimed to prepare suitable dosage forms which make these API suitable candidate for the studies. So, solubility enhancement of dosage form has increased the dissolution rate and thereby also improved the oral bioavailability. Developed pharmaceutical composition has available with improved dissolution and absorption. Developed composition Process has said effect, it has provided alternating soft gelatin formulation to hard gelatin capsule. Developed composition Process has said effect; it has provided alternating pellets formulation to conventional hard gelatin capsule. This composition also provided the opportunity to dose i.e the entire daily therapeutic dose of enzalutamide in two dosage units instead of four units. It is provided suitable single dose units/ two units with reasonable capsule size which comprising the prescribed amount of drug with advantageous dissolution and absorption

MATERIALS:

API Enzalutamide got a gift sample from BDR Pharmaceuticals International Pvt Ltd, Vanseti, Halol. solubilizers Caprylic/Capric Triglyceride were brought from Abitec AN ABF INGREDIENTS COMPANY, Mumbai. Caprylocaproyl macroglycerides from Mumbai. Methanol, Lactose Anhydrous, Cholesteryl sulfate, Acetonitrile, Caprylic acid from merck, Mumbai.

METHODOLOGY

FT-IR of Enzalutamide:

Identification of Enzalutamide was carried out by Infra-Red absorption spectroscopy (FT-IR). The infrared spectrum of the Enzalutamide was recorded on a Fourier Transformer Infra-Red Spectrophotometer in the range of $4000-400\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) of Enzalutamide

The thermogram of Enzalutamide was carried out by using differential scanning calorimeter (DSC), on Shimadzu TA-60 model (Shimadzu Corporation, Japan).

Preparation of calibration curve

The linearity of the detector response to different concentrations of Enzalutamide was studied in the range of 5– 50 ppm. Samples with different concentrations were analyzed.

Bulk density:

$$ABD = \frac{\text{Weight of the powder blend}}{\text{Untapped Volume of the packing}}$$

Tapped density:

$$TD = \frac{\text{Weight of the powder blend}}{\text{Tapped Volume of the packing}}$$

Compressibility index

$$C_I = \frac{(\text{Tapped density} - \text{Bulk density})}{\text{Tapped Density}} \times 100$$

Preparation method of enzalutamide capsules

Enzalutamide capsules were prepared using sequence of unit operation i.e. Granulation, Drying, Sifting, Lubrication, Capsule filling

Dissolution testing:

Type of Apparatus used was USP type II -Paddle apparatus maintained 50 RPM with 900 ml volume

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**Preformulation studies:**

Fig 1: Standard curve

Fig 2:FTIR studies of pure drug

Fig 3: XRD of pure drug:

Fig 4:DSC of pure drug

Fig 5:DSC of pure + excipients

Flow characteristics:

Table 1: solubility, bulk density, tapped density, housners ratio, carrs index values all formulation

Batch Name	Solubility (mg/mL)	Bulk Density (gm/mL)	Tapped Density (gm/mL)	Housner's Ratio	Carr's index %
FE-1	0.19±0.004	47	60	1.28	21.67
FE -2	0.201±0.005	47	61	1.30	22.95
FE -3	0.212±0.004	47	61	1.30	22.95
FE -4	0.214±0.004	48	60	1.25	20.00
FE -5	0.203±0.005	47	61	1.30	22.95
FE -6	0.215±0.006	48	61	1.27	21.31
FE -7	0.194±0.006	48	61	1.27	21.31
FE -8	0.213±0.006	48	61.3	1.28	21.70
FE -9	0.21±0.005	47	61.6	1.31	23.70
FE -10	0.211±0.005	47	61.7	1.31	23.82

FE -11	0.211±0.006	48	61.65	1.28	22.14
FE -12	0.21±0.006	48	61.2	1.28	21.57
FE -13	0.21±0.005	48	61.22	1.28	21.59

Table 2: disintegration, particle size, % yield, % drug content, dissolution of all formulations

Batch Number	Disintegration time (sec)	Particle Size (nm)	% yield	% Drug Content	Dissolution after 45 min (%)
FE-1	169.66±2.9	460	96%	98.89±0.54	86.18%±1.55
FE -2	171.5 ±2.73	318	96%	98.99±0.43	94.21%± 1.86
FE -3	171±2.96	421	97%	98.79±0.51	90.24%± 1.11
FE -4	171±1.41	415	97%	98.91±0.40	94.39%± 0.78
FE -5	170±1.91	430	97%	98.92±0.38	94.45%± 0.96
FE -6	170±2.09	430	97%	98.74±0.38	91.22%± 1.04
FE -7	172±1.78	317	97%	98.34±0.34	94.42%± 0.73
FE -8	168.22±2.01	441	97%	98.22±0.51	87.56%± 0.83
FE -9	170.51±1.95	320	97%	98.21±0.50	94.40%± 0.92
FE -10	171.55±1.95	325	97%	99.25±0.47	94.23%± 1.04
FE -11	170.45±1.78	336	97%	99.08±0.51	94.26%± 1.13
FE -12	170.32±1.74	339	97%	99.19±0.44	94.22%± 1.24
FE -13	172.5±1.88	342	97%	98.88±0.34	94.24%± 0.95

Table 3: Predicted and Practical Response for Enzalutamide Formulation

Batch Number	Concentration (mg)		Predicted Response		Practical Response	
			Dissolution after 45 min (%)	Solubility Mg/mL	Dissolution after 45 min (%)	Solubility Mg/mL
CE-1	162.59	Captex	95.214	0.214	95.11% ±	0.217
	160.68	Labrasol			0.93	
CE-2	160.27	Captex	95.020	0.213	95.04% ±	0.215
	154.44	Labrasol			0.88	
CE-3	168.24	Captex	94.554	0.212	94.61% ±	0.213
	149.44	Labrasol			1.11	

Table 4: Results Other Than Dissolution for Batch No.CE-1, CE-2 and CE-3

BATCH NAME	%YIELD	FLOW PROPERTY CARR'S INDEX %	% DRUG CONTENT
CE-1	97%	22.71	99.31±0.23
CE-2	97%	21.33	99.84±0.18
CE-3	97%	21.54	99.91±0.24

CONCLUSION:

The dissolution rate is the primary factor limiting for bioavailability of enzalutamide. Studies have shown that enzalutamide's bioavailability is notably higher when administered as an oral liquid solution. Thus, the goal of this pharmaceutical development program was to create a solid oral formulation of enzalutamide encapsulated in hard gelatin capsules, enhancing patient and commercial compliance. To improve dissolution, different solubilizers were screened, resulting in the selection of Labrasol (Caprylocaproyl macroglycerides) and Caprylic/Capric Triglyceride in varying ratios. The formulations were evaluated for physical characteristics such as disintegration, drug content, and in vitro dissolution. A notable invention involved a solution containing a polymer and a surfactant mix of fatty acids and sterols in a water-miscible solvent, forming a nanodispersion upon dilution. Among the formulations, FE-2, with a 1:2 ratio of Enzalutamide to Labrasol, demonstrated the best performance, achieving maximum in vitro drug release within 45 minutes. The in vitro dissolution studies showed significant improvement in the dissolution behavior of the innovative formulations. Overall, this investigation highlighted that the novel formulations provide a promising approach for enhancing the oral absorption and bioavailability of BCS class II drugs.

Refernces :

1. Agarwal, Rajesh., 2011. Pharmaceutical Processing—A Review on Wet Granulation Technology. *Int J Pharm Front Res.*, 1, pp. 65-83.
2. Standard high shear mixer [Internet]. 2017 [cited 10 July 2022].
3. Haron N, Zakaria J, Mohideen Batcha M. Recent advances in fluidized bed drying. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering.* 2017; 243:012038.
4. Ruihuan G, Jiamin Y, Haigang W. Investigation of Gas-Solids Flow Characteristics in a Conical Fluidized B [Internet]. 2016 [cited 10 July 2022]
5. Manufacture of Hard Gelatin Capsules - Pharmapproach.com [Internet]. Pharmapproach.com. 2022 [cited 10 July 2022].
6. Mali, A., 2016. Capsule Manufacturing Technology. [online
7. Moulvi, S., Thorat, Y. and Kamble, A., 2021. A review: manufacturing of capsule shell from natural sources. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, 9(7), pp.169-177.
8. Hardy, I., Fitzpatrick, S. and Booth, S., 2003. Rational design of powder formulations for tamp filling processes. *Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*, 55(12), pp.1593-1599.
9. Reddy, V., 2012. Capsule production – industrial view. *Journal of Global Trends in Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 3(4), pp.887-909.
10. Cole, G. ed., 1987. *Powder Characteristics for Capsule Filling.* British Pharmaceutical Press, pp.1-28.

11. Aliyu R, Lawal A, Chasta P., 2020. Capsules: Types, Manufacturing, Formulation, Quality Control Tests and, Packaging And Storage - A Comprehensive Review. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Sciences*, 6(8): pp. 93-104.
12. Gupta S, Kesarla R, Omri A., 2013. Formulation Strategies to Improve the Bioavailability of Poorly Absorbed Drugs with Special Emphasis on Self-Emulsifying Systems. *ISRN Pharmaceutics*. 2013, pp.1-16.
13. Price G, Patel D. Drug Bioavailability [Internet]. *Ncbi.nlm.nih.gov*. 2022 [cited 10 July 2022].
14. Ruiz M, Scioli Montoto S. Routes of Drug Administration. *ADME Processes in Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2018; pp. 97-133.
15. Horde G, Gupta V. Drug Clearance [Internet]. *Statpearls.com*. 2022 [cited 10 July 2022].
16. Borowy C, Ashurst J. Physiology, Zero and First Order Kinetics [Internet]. *Ncbi.nlm.nih.gov*. 2022 [cited 10 July 2022].
17. Factors Affecting Bioavailability | [Internet]. *Omicsonline.org*. 2022 [cited 10 July 2022].
18. ICH M9 guideline on biopharmaceutics classification system-based biowaivers [Internet]. *Ema.europa.eu*. 2022 [cited 10 July 2022].
19. Manallack D. The pKa Distribution of Drugs: Application to Drug Discovery. *Perspectives in Medicinal Chemistry*. 2007; 1:25-38.
20. Pharmaceutical dosage forms [Internet]. *Latam-edu.usp.org*. 2021 [cited 10 July 2022].

21. Polderman J, Braakman D., 1968. The relation between compression force and dissolution time of tablets. *Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*, 20(4), pp. 323-324.
22. Nimmo W., 1976. Drugs, Diseases and Altered Gastric Emptying. *Clinical Pharmacokinetics*; 1(3), pp. 189-203.
23. Wilkinson G., 1997. The effects of diet, aging and disease-states on presystemic elimination and oral drug bioavailability in humans. *Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews*; 27(2-3): pp.129-159.
24. Kimura T, Higaki K., 2002. Gastrointestinal Transit and Drug Absorption. *Biological & Pharmaceutical Bulletin*; 25(2), pp.149-164.
25. Bushra R, Aslam N, Khan A., 2011. Food Drug Interactions. *Oman Medical Journal*; 26(2), pp. 77-83.
26. Palleria C, Di Paolo A, Giofrè C, Caglioti C, Leuzzi G, Siniscalchi A, De Sarro G, Gallelli L., 2013. Pharmacokinetic drug-drug interaction and their implication in clinical management. *J Res Med Sci.*; 18(7), pp.601-610.
27. Khan A, Singh L., 2016. Various Techniques of Bioavailability Enhancement: A Review. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*; 6(3), pp. 34-41.
28. Savjani K, Gajjar A, Savjani J. Drug Solubility: Importance and Enhancement Techniques. *ISRN Pharmaceutics*. 2012; pp.1-10.
29. Dave, Nikunj & Joshi, Tejas., 2017. A Concise Review on Surfactants and Its Significance; *International Journal of Applied Chemistry*; 13, pp. 663-672.
30. Ohadi M, Shahravan A, Dehghan N, Eslaminejad T, Banat I, 2020. Use of Microbial Surfactant in Microemulsion Drug Delivery System: A Systematic Review of Drug Design, Development and Therapy;(14); pp. 541-550.